

 ψ -Hilfer and Hilfer fractional self adjoint operator analytic inequalities

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Abstract: We give here ψ -Hilfer and Hilfer fractional self adjoint operator inner product comparison, Poincaré, Sobolev and Opial type inequalities. At first we give right and left ψ -Hilfer fractional representation formulae in the self adjoint operator sense. Operator inequalities are based in the self adjoint operator order over a Hilbert space.

Key words: self adjoint operator, Hilbert space, ψ -Hilfer and Hilfer fractional derivatives, Poincaré inequality, Sobolev inequality, Opial inequality.

1. Background - I

Let A be a selfadjoint linear operator on a complex Hilbert space $(H; \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$. The Gelfand map establishes a $*$ -isometrically isomorphism Φ between the set $C(Sp(A))$ of all continuous functions defined on the spectrum of A , denoted $Sp(A)$, and the C^* -algebra $C^*(A)$ generated by A and the identity operator 1_H on H as follows (see e.g. [5, p. 3]):

For any $f, g \in C(Sp(A))$ and any $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ we have

$$(i) \quad \Phi(\alpha f + \beta g) = \alpha \Phi(f) + \beta \Phi(g);$$

$$(ii) \quad \Phi(fg) = \Phi(f)\Phi(g) \text{ (the operation composition is on the right) and } \Phi(\overline{f}) = (\Phi(f))^*;$$

$$(iii) \quad \|\Phi(f)\| = \|f\| := \sup_{t \in Sp(A)} |f(t)|;$$

$$(iv) \quad \Phi(f_0) = 1_H \text{ and } \Phi(f_1) = A, \text{ where } f_0(t) = 1 \text{ and } f_1(t) = t, \text{ for } t \in Sp(A).$$

With this notation we define

$$f(A) := \Phi(f), \text{ for all } f \in C(Sp(A)),$$

and we call it the continuous functional calculus for a selfadjoint operator A .

If A is a selfadjoint operator and f is a real valued continuous function on $Sp(A)$ then $f(t) \geq 0$ for any $t \in Sp(A)$ implies that $f(A) \geq 0$, i.e. $f(A)$ is a positive operator on H . Moreover, if both f and g are real valued continuous functions on $Sp(A)$ then the following important property holds:

(P) $f(t) \geq g(t)$ for any $t \in Sp(A)$, implies that $f(A) \geq g(A)$ in the operator order of $B(H)$ (the Banach algebra of all bounded linear operators from H into itself).

Equivalently, we use (see [4], pp. 7-8):

Let U be a selfadjoint operator on the complex Hilbert space $(H, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ with the spectrum $Sp(U)$ included in the interval $[m, M]$ for some real numbers $m < M$ and $\{E_\lambda\}_\lambda$ be its spectral family.

Then for any continuous function $f : [m, M] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, it is well known that we have the following spectral representation in terms of the Riemann-Stieljes integral:

$$\langle f(U)x, y \rangle = \int_{m-0}^M f(\lambda) d(\langle E_\lambda x, y \rangle), \quad (1)$$

for any $x, y \in H$. The function $g_{x,y}(\lambda) := \langle E_\lambda x, y \rangle$ is of bounded variation on the interval $[m, M]$, and

$$g_{x,y}(m-0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad g_{x,y}(M) = \langle x, y \rangle, \quad (2)$$

for any $x, y \in H$. Furthermore, it is known that $g_x(\lambda) := \langle E_\lambda x, x \rangle$ is increasing and right continuous on $[m, M]$.

We have also the formula

$$\langle f(U)x, x \rangle = \int_{m-0}^M f(\lambda) d(\langle E_\lambda x, x \rangle), \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (3)$$

As a symbol we can write

$$f(U) = \int_{m-0}^M f(\lambda) dE_\lambda. \quad (4)$$

Above, $m = \min \{\lambda | \lambda \in Sp(U)\} := \min Sp(U)$, $M = \max \{\lambda | \lambda \in Sp(U)\} := \max Sp(U)$. The projections $\{E_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}}$, are called the spectral family of A , with the properties:

- (a) $E_\lambda \leq E_{\lambda'}$ for $\lambda \leq \lambda'$;
- (b) $E_{m-0} = 0_H$ (zero operator), $E_M = 1_H$ (identity operator) and $E_{\lambda+0} = E_\lambda$ for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$.

Furthermore

$$E_\lambda := \varphi_\lambda(U), \quad \forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R},$$

is a projection which reduces U , with

$$\varphi_\lambda(s) := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{for } -\infty < s \leq \lambda, \\ 0, & \text{for } \lambda < s < +\infty. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The spectral family $\{E_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \mathbb{R}}$ determines uniquely the self-adjoint operator U and vice versa.

For more on the topic see [6], pp. 256-266, and for more details see there pp. 157-266. See also [3].

Some more basics are given (we follow [4], pp. 1-5):

Let $(H; \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ be a Hilbert space over $\mathbb{C}$. A bounded linear operator A defined on H is selfjoint, i.e., $A = A^*$, iff $\langle Ax, x \rangle \in \mathbb{R}$, $\forall x \in H$, and if A is selfadjoint, then

$$\|A\| = \sup_{x \in H: \|x\|=1} |\langle Ax, x \rangle|. \quad (6)$$

Let A, B be selfadjoint operators on H . Then $A \leq B$ iff $\langle Ax, x \rangle \leq \langle Bx, x \rangle$, $\forall x \in H$.

In particular, A is called positive if $A \geq 0$.

Denote by

$$\mathcal{P} := \left\{ \varphi(s) := \sum_{k=0}^n \alpha_k s^k \mid n \geq 0, \alpha_k \in \mathbb{C}, 0 \leq k \leq n \right\}. \quad (7)$$

If $A \in \mathcal{B}(H)$ is selfadjoint, and $\varphi(s) \in \mathcal{P}$ has real coefficients, then $\varphi(A)$ is selfadjoint, and

$$\|\varphi(A)\| = \max \{|\varphi(\lambda)|, \lambda \in Sp(A)\}. \quad (8)$$

If φ is any function defined on $\mathbb{R}$ we define

$$\|\varphi\|_A := \sup \{|\varphi(\lambda)|, \lambda \in Sp(A)\}. \quad (9)$$

If A is selfadjoint operator on Hilbert space H and φ is continuous and given that $\varphi(A)$ is selfadjoint, then $\|\varphi(A)\| = \|\varphi\|_A$. And if φ is a continuous real valued function so it is $|\varphi|$, then $\varphi(A)$ and $|\varphi|(A) = |\varphi(A)|$ are selfadjoint operators (by [4], p. 4, Theorem 7).

Hence it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \|\|\varphi(A)\|\| &= \|\|\varphi\|\|_A = \sup \{\|\varphi(\lambda)\|, \lambda \in Sp(A)\} \\ &= \sup \{|\varphi(\lambda)|, \lambda \in Sp(A)\} = \|\varphi\|_A = \|\varphi(A)\|, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

that is

$$\|\|\varphi(A)\|\| = \|\varphi(A)\|. \quad (11)$$

For a selfadjoint operator $A \in \mathcal{B}(H)$ which is positive, there exists a unique positive selfadjoint operator $B := \sqrt{A} \in \mathcal{B}(H)$ such that $B^2 = A$, that is $(\sqrt{A})^2 = A$. We call B the square root of A .

Let $A \in \mathcal{B}(H)$, then A^*A is selfadjoint and positive. Define the "operator absolute value" $|A| := \sqrt{A^*A}$. If $A = A^*$, then $|A| = \sqrt{A^2}$.

For a continuous real valued function φ we observe the following:

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi(A)| \text{ (the functional absolute value)} &= \int_{m-0}^M |\varphi(\lambda)| dE_\lambda = \\ \int_{m-0}^M \sqrt{(\varphi(\lambda))^2} dE_\lambda &= \sqrt{(\varphi(A))^2} = |\varphi(A)| \text{ (operator absolute value)}, \end{aligned}$$

where A is a selfadjoint operator.

That is we have

$$|\varphi(A)| \text{ (functional absolute value)} = |\varphi(A)| \text{ (operator absolute value)}. \quad (12)$$

2. Background - II

Let $-\infty < a < b < \infty$, the left and right Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals of order $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ ($\mathcal{R}(\alpha) > 0$) are defined by

$$(I_{a+}^\alpha f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (13)$$

$x > a$; where Γ stands for the gamma function,

and

$$(I_b^\alpha f)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (14)$$

$x < b$.

The Riemann-Liouville left and right fractional derivatives of order $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ ($\mathcal{R}(\alpha) \geq 0$) are defined by

$$(\Delta_{a+}^{\alpha} y)(x) = \left(\frac{d}{dx}\right)^n (I_{a+}^{n-\alpha} y)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{dx}\right)^n \int_a^x (x-t)^{n-\alpha-1} y(t) dt \quad (15)$$

($n = \lceil \mathcal{R}(\alpha) \rceil$, $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ means ceiling of the number; $x > a$)

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta_{b-}^{\alpha} y)(x) &= (-1)^n \left(\frac{d}{dx}\right)^n (I_{b-}^{n-\alpha} y)(x) = \\ &= \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(\frac{d}{dx}\right)^n \int_x^b (t-x)^{n-\alpha-1} y(t) dt \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

($n = \lceil \mathcal{R}(\alpha) \rceil$; $x < b$), respectively, where $\mathcal{R}(\alpha)$ is the real part of α .

In particular, when $\alpha = n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, then

$$(\Delta_{a+}^0 y)(x) = (\Delta_{b-}^0 y)(x) = y(x);$$

$$(\Delta_{a+}^n y)(x) = y^{(n)}(x), \text{ and } (\Delta_{b-}^n y)(x) = (-1)^n y^{(n)}(x), \quad n \in \mathbb{N},$$

see [9].

Let $\alpha > 0$, $I = [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$, f an integrable function defined on I and $\psi \in C^1(I)$ an increasing function such that $\psi'(x) \neq 0$, for all $x \in I$. Left fractional integrals and left Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives of a function f with respect to another function ψ are defined as ([7], [9])

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \psi'(t) (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (17)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) &= \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx}\right)^n I_{a+}^{n-\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx}\right)^n \int_a^x \psi'(t) (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{n-\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

respectively, where $n = \lceil \alpha \rceil$.

Similarly, we define the right ones:

$$I_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad (19)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) &= \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx}\right)^n I_{b-}^{n-\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx}\right)^n \int_x^b \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{n-\alpha-1} f(t) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The following semigroup property holds; if $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $f \in C(I)$, then

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} I_{a+}^{\beta, \psi} f = I_{a+}^{\alpha+\beta, \psi} f \quad \text{and} \quad I_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} I_{b-}^{\beta, \psi} f = I_{b-}^{\alpha+\beta, \psi} f.$$

Next let again $\alpha > 0$, $n = [\alpha]$, $I = [a, b]$, $f, \psi \in C^n(I)$: ψ is increasing and $\psi'(x) \neq 0$, for all $x \in I$. The left ψ -Caputo fractional derivative of f of order α is given by ([1])

$${}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = I_{a+}^{n-\alpha, \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n f(x), \quad (21)$$

and the right ψ -Caputo fractional derivative ([1])

$${}^C D_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = I_{b-}^{n-\alpha, \psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n f(x). \quad (22)$$

We set

$$f_{\psi}^{[n]}(x) := f_{\psi}^{(n)} f(x) := \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n f(x). \quad (23)$$

Clearly, when $\alpha = m \in \mathbb{N}$ we have

$${}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = f_{\psi}^{[m]}(x) \quad \text{and} \quad {}^C D_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = (-1)^m f_{\psi}^{[m]}(x),$$

and if $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$, then

$${}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^x \psi'(t) (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{n-\alpha-1} f_{\psi}^{[n]}(t) dt, \quad (24)$$

and

$${}^C D_{b-}^{\alpha, \psi} f(x) = \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_x^b \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{n-\alpha-1} f_{\psi}^{[n]}(t) dt. \quad (25)$$

If $\psi(x) = x$, then we get the usual left and right Caputo fractional derivatives

$${}^C D_{a+}^m f(x) = f^{(m)}(x), \quad {}^C D_{b-}^m f(x) = (-1)^m f^{(m)}(x),$$

for $m \in \mathbb{N}$, and ($\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$)

$$D_{*a}^{\alpha} f(x) = {}^C D_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{n-\alpha-1} f^{(n)}(t) dt, \quad (26)$$

$$D_{b-}^{\alpha}(x) = {}^C D_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{n-\alpha-1} f^{(n)}(t) dt. \quad (27)$$

Also we set

$${}^C D_{a+}^{0, \psi} f(x) = {}^C D_{b-}^{0, \psi} f(x) = f(x).$$

Next we will deal with the ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative.

Definition 2.1. ([11]) Let $n - 1 < \alpha < n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $I = [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ and $f, \psi \in C^n([a, b])$, ψ is increasing and $\psi'(x) \neq 0$, for all $x \in I$. The ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative (left-sided and right-sided) ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+(b-)}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f$ of order α and type $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, respectively, are defined by

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = I_{a+}^{\beta(n-\alpha); \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f(x), \quad (28)$$

and

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = I_{b-}^{\beta(n-\alpha); \psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f(x), \quad x \in [a, b]. \quad (29)$$

The original Hilfer fractional derivatives ([10]) come from $\psi(x) = x$, and are denoted by ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(x)$ and ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(x)$.

When $\beta = 0$, we get Riemann-Liouville fractional derivatives, while when $\beta = 1$ we have Caputo type fractional derivatives.

We define $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha)$. We notice that $n - 1 < \alpha \leq \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha) \leq \alpha + n - \alpha = n$, hence $[\gamma] = n$. We can easily write that ([11])

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = I_{a+}^{\gamma-\alpha; \psi} \Delta_{a+}^{\gamma; \psi} f(x), \quad (30)$$

and

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = I_{b-}^{\gamma-\alpha; \psi} \Delta_{b-}^{\gamma; \psi} f(x), \quad x \in [a, b]. \quad (31)$$

We have that ([11])

$$\Delta_{a+}^{\gamma; \psi} f(x) = \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f(x), \quad (32)$$

and

$$\Delta_{b-}^{\gamma; \psi} f(x) = \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f(x). \quad (33)$$

In particular, when $0 < \alpha < 1$ and $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$; $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(1 - \alpha)$, we have that

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma - \alpha)} \int_a^x \psi'(t) (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{\gamma-\alpha-1} \Delta_{a+}^{\gamma; \psi} f(t) dt, \quad (34)$$

and

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma - \alpha)} \int_x^b \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{\gamma-\alpha-1} \Delta_{b-}^{\gamma; \psi} f(t) dt, \quad (35)$$

$x \in [a, b]$.

Remark 2.1. ([11]) Let $\mu = n(1 - \beta) + \beta\alpha$, then $[\mu] = n$.

Assume that $g(x) = I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f(x) \in C^n([a, b])$, we have that

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(x) = I_{a+}^{n-\mu; \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n g(x). \quad (36)$$

Thus

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f = {}^C D_{a+}^{\mu;\psi} g(x) = {}^C D_{a+}^{\mu;\psi} \left[I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f(x) \right]. \quad (37)$$

Assume that $w(x) = I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f(x) \in C^n([a, b])$. Hence

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(x) = I_{b-}^{\beta(n-\alpha);\psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n w(x) = I_{b-}^{n-\mu;\psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(x)} \frac{d}{dx} \right)^n w(x). \quad (38)$$

Thus

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f = {}^C D_{b-}^{\mu;\psi} w(x) = {}^C D_{b-}^{\mu;\psi} \left(I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f(x) \right). \quad (39)$$

We mention the simplified ψ -Hilfer fractional Taylor formulae:

Theorem 2.1. (see also [11]) Let $\psi, f \in C^n([a, b])$, with ψ being increasing such that $\psi'(x) \neq 0$ over $[a, b]$, where $n - 1 < \alpha < n$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, and $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha)$, $x \in [a, b]$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) - \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(\psi(x) - \psi(a))^{\gamma-k}}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (a) = \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \psi'(t) (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{a+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt, \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) - \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^k (\psi(b) - \psi(x))^{\gamma-k}}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (b) = \\ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{b-}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Here notice that $\left(I_{a+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (a) = \left(I_{b-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (b) = 0$.

3. Main Results

Let A be a selfadjoint operator on the Hilbert space H with the spectrum $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$, $m < M$; $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$.

In the next we obtain ψ -Hilfer and Hilfer fractional comparison, Poincaré, Sobolev and Opial type inequalities in the operator order of $B(H)$ (the Banach algebra of all bounded linear operators from H into itself). All of our functions from now on in this article are real valued.

We give at first the following ψ -Hilfer fractional operator representation formulae:

Theorem 3.1. Let A be a selfadjoint operator on the Hilbert space H with the spectrum $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$ for some real numbers $m < M$, $\{E_{\lambda}\}_{\lambda}$ be its spectral family and I be a closed subinterval on $\mathbb{R}$ with $[m, M] \subset \overset{\circ}{I}$ (the interior of I). Let $\psi, f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $\psi, f \in C^n([m, M])$, with ψ being increasing and $\psi'(\lambda) \neq 0$ over $[m, M]$, where $n - 1 < \alpha < n$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, and $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha)$, $\lambda \in [m, M]$.

Then

i)

$$f(A) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (m)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\gamma-k} \quad (42)$$

$$+ R_n^{(1)}(f, \psi, m, M),$$

where

$$R_n^{(1)}(f, \psi, m, M) :=$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^{\lambda} \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H \mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_{\lambda}, \quad (43)$$

and

ii)

$$f(A) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^k f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (M)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} (\psi(M) 1_H - \psi(A))^{\gamma-k} \quad (44)$$

$$+ R_n^{(2)}(f, \psi, m, M),$$

where

$$R_n^{(2)}(f, \psi, m, M) :=$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H \mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_{\lambda}. \quad (45)$$

Proof. By Theorem 2.1 we have

$$f(\lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\gamma-k}}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (m) + \quad (46)$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^{\lambda} \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H \mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt,$$

and

$$f(\lambda) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^k (\psi(M) - \psi(\lambda))^{\gamma-k}}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (M) + \quad (47)$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H \mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt,$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Then we integrate (46), (47) against E_{λ} to get

$$\int_{m-0}^M f(\lambda) dE_{\lambda} = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (m)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} \int_{m-0}^M (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\gamma-k} dE_{\lambda} +$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^\lambda \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_\lambda, \quad (48)$$

and

$$\int_{m-0}^M f(\lambda) dE_\lambda = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^k f_\psi^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (M)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} \int_{m-0}^M (\psi(M) - \psi(\lambda))^{\gamma-k} dE_\lambda + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_\lambda^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_\lambda. \quad (49)$$

By the spectral representation theorem we obtain

$$f(A) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{f_\psi^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (m)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\gamma-k} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^\lambda \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_\lambda, \quad (50)$$

and

$$f(A) = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{(-1)^k f_\psi^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (M)}{\Gamma(\gamma - k + 1)} (\psi(M) 1_H - \psi(A))^{\gamma-k} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_\lambda^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_\lambda, \quad (51)$$

proving the claim. $\square$

We make

Remark 3.1. (to Theorem 3.1) Assume that $f_\psi^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (m) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, then (see (40))

$$f(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^\lambda \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt, \quad (52)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Hence it holds

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^\alpha, \quad (53)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

If $\alpha > 1$, by (52) we get

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{(\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) \right| d\psi(t) \leq$$

$$\frac{(\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^M \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) \right| d\psi(t). \quad (54)$$

That is, when $\alpha > 1$, we obtained

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f \right\|_{L_1([m,M],\psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha-1}, \quad (55)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Next, let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. Then, by (52) and Hölder's inequality, we derive

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m,M],\psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha-1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}, \quad (56)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

By (42), (43) and $f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha);\psi} f \right) (m) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, we have

$$f(A) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^{\lambda} \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_{\lambda}. \quad (57)$$

Therefore it holds

$$\langle f(A)x, y \rangle = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^{\lambda} \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) d \langle E_{\lambda} x, y \rangle, \quad (58)$$

$\forall x, y \in H$.

The function $g_{x,y}(\lambda) := \langle E_{\lambda} x, y \rangle$ is of bounded variation on $[m, M]$, $g_{x,y}(m-0) = 0$ and $g_{x,y}(M) = \langle x, y \rangle$, $\forall x, y \in H$.

It is also well known that $g_x(\lambda) := \langle E_{\lambda} x, x \rangle$ is nondecreasing and right continuous on $[m, M]$. One has

$$\langle f(A)x, x \rangle = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_m^{\lambda} \psi'(t) (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(t))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f(t) dt \right) d \langle E_{\lambda} x, x \rangle, \quad (59)$$

$\forall x \in H$.

Therefore it holds

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \stackrel{(53)}{\leq} \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \int_{m-0}^M (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha} d \langle E_{\lambda} x, x \rangle = \quad (60)$$

$$\frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta;\psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\alpha} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H.$$

Similarly, when $\alpha > 1$, by (55), we get

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M (\psi(\lambda) - \psi(m))^{\alpha-1} d\langle E_\lambda x, x \rangle = \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^{\alpha-1} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (61)$$

Let now $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. Then, by (56) we derive

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)(p(\alpha-1)+1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^{\alpha-\frac{1}{q}} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (62)$$

We have proved the following ψ -Hilfer fractional left side comparison results.

Theorem 3.2. All as in Theorem 3.1, plus $f_\psi^{[n-k]} \left(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (m) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$. Then

i)

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^\alpha x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (63)$$

Inequality (63) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \|(\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^\alpha\|, \quad (64)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^\alpha. \quad (65)$$

ii) when $\alpha > 1$ we have

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^{\alpha-1} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (66)$$

Inequality (66) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \|(\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^{\alpha-1}\|, \quad (67)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\|H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\psi(A) - \psi(m)1_H)^{\alpha-1}. \quad (68)$$

iii) when $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$, we have

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m^+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\langle (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}} x, x \right\rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (69)$$

Inequality (69) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m^+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}} \right\|, \quad (70)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m^+}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} (\psi(A) - \psi(m) 1_H)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}. \quad (71)$$

We make

Remark 3.2. (to Theorem 3.1) Here we assume that $f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M^-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (M) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$, then (see (41))

$$f(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt, \quad (72)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Hence it holds

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (\psi(M) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha}, \quad (73)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

If $\alpha > 1$, we get

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\psi(M) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1}, \quad (74)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Next, let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. Then

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} (\psi(M) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}, \quad (75)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Here also it holds (by (44), (45))

$$f(A) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt \right) dE_{\lambda}. \quad (76)$$

Consequently we have

$$\langle f(A)x, y \rangle = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt \right) d \langle E_{\lambda} x, y \rangle, \quad (77)$$

$\forall x, y \in H$.

In particular we have

$$\langle f(A)x, x \rangle = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{m-0}^M \left(\int_{\lambda}^M \psi'(t) (\psi(t) - \psi(\lambda))^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f(t) dt \right) d \langle E_{\lambda} x, x \rangle, \quad (78)$$

$\forall x \in H$.

We state the following ψ -Hilfer fractional right side comparison results.

Theorem 3.3. All as in Theorem 3.1, plus $f_{\psi}^{[n-k]} \left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha); \psi} f \right) (M) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n-1$. Then

i)

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \langle (\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (79)$$

Inequality (79) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \|(\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha}\|, \quad (80)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{\infty, [m, M]}}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} (\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha}. \quad (81)$$

ii) when $\alpha > 1$ we have

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \langle (\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha-1} x, x \rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (82)$$

Inequality (82) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \|(\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha-1}\|, \quad (83)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_1([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} (\psi(M) \mathbf{1}_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha-1}. \quad (84)$$

iii) when $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$, we have

$$|\langle f(A)x, x \rangle| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\langle (\psi(M)1_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}} x, x \right\rangle, \quad \forall x \in H. \quad (85)$$

Inequality (85) means that

$$\|f(A)\| \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| (\psi(M)1_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}} \right\|, \quad (86)$$

and in particular

$$f(A) \leq \frac{\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M^-}^{\alpha, \beta; \psi} f \right\|_{L_q([m, M], \psi)}}{\Gamma(\alpha) (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} (\psi(M)1_H - \psi(A))^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}. \quad (87)$$

Proof. Similar to the proof of Theorem 3.2, by the use of Remark 3.2. $\square$

We need

Definition 3.1. Let the real valued function $f \in C([m, M])$, and we consider

$$g(t) = \int_m^t f(z) dz, \quad \forall t \in [m, M], \quad (88)$$

then $g \in C([m, M])$.

We denote by

$$\int_{m1_H}^A f := \Phi(g) = g(A). \quad (89)$$

We understand and write that ($r > 0$)

$$g^r(A) = \Phi(g^r) =: \left(\int_{m1_H}^A f \right)^r. \quad (90)$$

Clearly $\left(\int_{m1_H}^A f \right)^r$ is a self adjoint operator on H , for any $r > 0$.

Definition 3.2. Let $f : [m, M] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous. We consider

$$g(t) = \int_t^M f(z) dz, \quad \forall t \in [m, M], \quad (91)$$

then $g \in C([m, M])$.

We denote by

$$\int_A^{M1_H} f := \Phi(g) = g(A). \quad (92)$$

We denote also

$$g^r(A) = \Phi(g^r) =: \left(\int_A^{M1_H} f \right)^r, \quad r > 0. \quad (93)$$

Clearly $\left(\int_A^{M1_H} f \right)^r$ is a self adjoint operator on H , for any $r > 0$.

We mention the following Hilfer fractional derivatives representation formulae:

Theorem 3.4. ([2]) Let $\alpha > 0$, $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$, $[\alpha] = n$, $0 < \beta < 1$; $f \in C^n([m, M])$, $[m, M] \subset \mathbb{R}$; and set $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha)$. Assume further that $\Delta_{m+}^\gamma f \in C([a, b]) : \Delta_{m+}^{\gamma-j} f(m) = 0$, for $j = 1, \dots, n$. Let also $\bar{\alpha} > 0 : [\bar{\alpha}] = \bar{n}$, with $\bar{\gamma} = \bar{\alpha} + \beta(\bar{n} - \bar{\alpha})$, and assume that $\alpha > \bar{\alpha}$ and $\gamma > \bar{\gamma}$. Then

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})} \int_m^\lambda (\lambda - t)^{\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) dt, \quad (94)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$,

furthermore ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \in AC([m, M])$ (absolutely continuous functions) if $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} \geq 1$ and ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \in C([m, M])$ if $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} \in (0, 1)$.

Theorem 3.5. ([2]) Let $\alpha > 0$, $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$, $[\alpha] = n$, $0 < \beta < 1$; $f \in C^n([m, M])$, $[m, M] \subset \mathbb{R}$; and set $\gamma = \alpha + \beta(n - \alpha)$. Assume further that $\Delta_{M-}^\gamma f \in C([a, b]) : \Delta_{M-}^{\gamma-j} f(M) = 0$, $j = 1, \dots, n$. Let also $\bar{\alpha} > 0 : [\bar{\alpha}] = \bar{n}$, with $\bar{\gamma} = \bar{\alpha} + \beta(\bar{n} - \bar{\alpha})$, and assume that $\alpha > \bar{\alpha}$ and $\gamma > \bar{\gamma}$. Then

$${}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})} \int_\lambda^M (t - \lambda)^{\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) dt, \quad (95)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$,

furthermore ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \in AC([m, M])$ if $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} \geq 1$ and ${}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \in C([m, M])$ if $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} \in (0, 1)$.

We mention the following left and right Hilfer fractional Poincaré type inequalities:

Theorem 3.6. ([2]) All as in Theorem 3.4, $0 \leq \beta < 1$. Let also $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and assume that $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} > \frac{1}{q}$. Then

$$\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \right\|_{q, [m, \lambda]} \leq \frac{(\lambda - m)^{\alpha - \bar{\alpha}}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) (q(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}))^{\frac{1}{q}} (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right\|_{q, [m, \lambda]}, \quad (96)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Theorem 3.7. ([2]) All as in Theorem 3.5, $0 \leq \beta < 1$. Let also $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and assume that $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} > \frac{1}{q}$. Then

$$\left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \right\|_{q, [\lambda, M]} \leq \frac{(M - \lambda)^{\alpha - \bar{\alpha}}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) (q(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}))^{\frac{1}{q}} (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left\| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right\|_{q, [\lambda, M]}, \quad (97)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

We present the following left Hilfer fractional operator Poincaré type inequality.

Theorem 3.8. *Let A be a selfadjoint operator on the Hilbert space H with the spectrum $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$ for some real numbers $m < M$. We suppose also the assumptions of Theorem 3.6. Then*

$$\int_{m1_H}^A \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \right|^q \leq \frac{(A - m1_H)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})q}}{(\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}))^q (q(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})) (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)^{q-1}} \left(\int_{m1_H}^A \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right|^q \right). \quad (98)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.6 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. □

We present also the following right Hilfer fractional operator Poincaré type inequality.

Theorem 3.9. *The setting as in Theorem 3.8, but now under the assumptions of Theorem 3.7. Then*

$$\int_A^{M1_H} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f \right|^q \leq \frac{(M1_H - A)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})q}}{(\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}))^q (q(\alpha - \bar{\alpha})) (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)^{q-1}} \left(\int_A^{M1_H} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right|^q \right). \quad (99)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.7 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. □

Next we mention some Hilfer fractional left and right Opial type inequalities ([8]).

Theorem 3.10. ([2]) *Let all as in Theorem 3.4, $0 \leq \beta < 1$. Let also $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, and assume that $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} > \frac{1}{q}$. Then*

$$\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f(w) \right| \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(w) \right| dw \leq \frac{2^{-\frac{1}{q}} (\lambda - m)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) + (\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q})}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) [(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1) (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 2)]^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(w) \right|^q dw \right)^{\frac{2}{q}}, \quad (100)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Theorem 3.11. ([2]) *Let all as in Theorem 3.5, $0 \leq \beta < 1$. Let also $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, and assume that $\alpha - \bar{\alpha} > \frac{1}{q}$. Then*

$$\int_\lambda^M \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha}, \beta} f(w) \right| \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(w) \right| dw \leq \frac{2^{-\frac{1}{q}} (M - \lambda)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) + (\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q})}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) [(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1) (p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 2)]^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\int_\lambda^M \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(w) \right|^q dw \right)^{\frac{2}{q}}, \quad (101)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

We give the following operator Hilfer fractional left and right Opial type inequalities. These come by the use of Theorems 3.10, 3.11 and property (P) with (ii), see section 1.

Theorem 3.12. *All as in Theorem 3.10. Then*

$$\int_{m1_H}^A \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\bar{\alpha},\beta} f \right| \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f \right| \leq \frac{2^{-\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) [(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 2)]^{\frac{1}{p}}}$$

$$(A - m1_H)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) + (\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q})} \left(\int_{m1_H}^A \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f \right|^q \right)^{\frac{2}{q}}. \quad (102)$$

Theorem 3.13. *All as in Theorem 3.11. Then*

$$\int_A^{M1_H} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\bar{\alpha},\beta} f \right| \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha,\beta} f \right| \leq \frac{2^{-\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) [(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 1)(p(\alpha - \bar{\alpha} - 1) + 2)]^{\frac{1}{p}}}$$

$$(M1_H - A)^{(\alpha - \bar{\alpha}) + (\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{q})} \left(\int_A^{M1_H} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha,\beta} f \right|^q \right)^{\frac{2}{q}}. \quad (103)$$

We give the following Hilfer left fractional Poincaré type inequality.

Theorem 3.14. *Let $f \in C^n([m, M])$, $n - 1 < \alpha < n$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$. Assume that $(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha)} f)^{(n-k)}(m) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$. Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. Then*

$$\int_m^\lambda |f(\lambda_1)|^q d\lambda_1 \leq \frac{(\lambda - m)^{\alpha q}}{(\alpha q) (\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{(q-1)}} \int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(t) \right|^q dt, \quad (104)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Proof. Assume $(I_{m+}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha)} f)^{(n-k)}(m) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$, then (see (40))

$$f(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^\lambda (\lambda - t)^{\alpha-1} {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(t) dt, \quad (105)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. By Hölder's inequality we obtain

$$|f(\lambda)| \leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_m^\lambda (\lambda - t)^{\alpha-1} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(t) \right| dt \leq$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \frac{(\lambda - m)^{\frac{(p(\alpha-1)+1)}{p}}}{(p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} =$$

$$\frac{(\lambda - m)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)(p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}, \quad \forall \lambda \in [m, M]. \quad (106)$$

One can write

$$|f(\lambda_1)| \leq \frac{(\lambda_1 - m)^{\alpha - \frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)(p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left(\int_m^{\lambda_1} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}, \quad (107)$$

$\forall \lambda_1 \in [m, \lambda]$, where $\lambda \in [m, M]$.

That is

$$|f(\lambda_1)|^q \leq \frac{(\lambda_1 - m)^{\alpha q - 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{q}{p}}} \left(\int_m^{\lambda_1} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right), \quad (108)$$

$\forall \lambda_1 \in [m, \lambda]$.

Consequently, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \int_m^\lambda |f(\lambda_1)|^q d\lambda_1 &\leq \frac{\left(\int_m^\lambda (\lambda_1 - m)^{\alpha q - 1} d\lambda_1 \right)}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{q}{p}}} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right) = \\ &\frac{(\lambda - m)^{\alpha q}}{(\alpha q) (\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{q-1}} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right), \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$, proving the claim. $\square$

We also give the following Hilfer right fractional Poincaré type inequality.

Theorem 3.15. *Let $f \in C^n([m, M])$, $n - 1 < \alpha < n$, $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$. Assume that $\left(I_{M-}^{(1-\beta)(n-\alpha)} f \right)^{(n-k)}(M) = 0$, $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$. Let $p, q > 1 : \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, with $\alpha > \frac{1}{q}$. Then*

$$\int_\lambda^M |f(\lambda_1)|^q d\lambda_1 \leq \frac{(M - \lambda)^{\alpha q}}{(\alpha q) (\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{(q-1)}} \int_\lambda^M \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt, \quad (110)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Proof. As similar to the proof of Theorem 3.14 is omitted. We use (41), etc. $\square$

Next comes a Hilfer left fractional Sobolev type inequality.

Theorem 3.16. *All as in Theorem 3.14 and $r \geq 1$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} \int_m^\lambda |f(\lambda_1)|^r d\lambda_1 &\leq \\ &\frac{(\lambda - m)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q}) + 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}} \left(r \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{q} \right) + 1 \right)} \left(\int_m^\lambda \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}, \end{aligned} \quad (111)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Proof. By (107) and $r \geq 1$, we find

$$|f(\lambda_1)|^r \leq \frac{(\lambda_1 - m)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q})}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}}} \left(\int_m^{\lambda_1} |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}, \quad (112)$$

$\forall \lambda_1 \in [m, \lambda]$, where $\lambda \in [m, M]$.

Consequently, it holds

$$\begin{aligned} \int_m^{\lambda} |f(\lambda_1)|^r d\lambda_1 &\leq \frac{\int_m^{\lambda} (\lambda_1 - m)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q})} d\lambda_1}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}}} \left(\int_m^{\lambda} |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{r}{q}} = \\ &\frac{(\lambda - m)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q}) + 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}} \left(r \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{q} \right) + 1 \right)} \left(\int_m^{\lambda} |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}, \end{aligned} \quad (113)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$. The claim is proved. $\square$

It follows the Hilfer right fractional Sobolev type inequality.

Theorem 3.17. *All as in Theorem 3.15 and $r \geq 1$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\lambda}^M |f(\lambda_1)|^r d\lambda_1 &\leq \frac{(M - \lambda)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q}) + 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}} \left(r \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{q} \right) + 1 \right)} \\ &\left(\int_{\lambda}^M |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(t)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}, \end{aligned} \quad (114)$$

$\forall \lambda \in [m, M]$.

Proof. As similar to the proof of Theorem 3.16 is omitted. $\square$

Next come left and right operator Hilfer fractional Poincaré type inequalities.

Theorem 3.18. *Let A be a selfadjoint operator on the Hilbert space H with $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$, $m < M$. We suppose all as in Theorem 3.14. Then*

$$\int_{m1_H}^A |f|^q \leq \frac{(A - m1_H)^{\alpha q}}{(\alpha q) (\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{q-1}} \left(\int_{m1_H}^A |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f|^q \right). \quad (115)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.14 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. $\square$

Theorem 3.19. *Let A be a selfadjoint operator on H with $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$, $m < M$. We suppose all as in Theorem 3.15. Then*

$$\int_A^{M1_H} |f|^q \leq \frac{(M1_H - A)^{\alpha q}}{(\alpha q) (\Gamma(\alpha))^q (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{q-1}} \left(\int_A^{M1_H} |{}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f|^q \right). \quad (116)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.15 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. $\square$

We finish with operator Hilfer left and right fractional Sobolev type inequalities.

Theorem 3.20. *Let A be a selfadjoint operator on H with $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$, $m < M$. We suppose all as in Theorem 3.16. Then*

$$\int_{m1_H}^A |f|^r \leq \frac{(A - m1_H)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q}) + 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}} \left(r \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{q} + 1 \right) \right)} \left(\int_{m1_H}^A \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{m+}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right|^q \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}. \quad (117)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.16 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. $\square$

Theorem 3.21. *Let A be a selfadjoint operator on H with $Sp(A) \subseteq [m, M]$, $m < M$. We suppose all as in Theorem 3.17. Then*

$$\int_A^{M1_H} |f|^r \leq \frac{(M1_H - A)^{r(\alpha - \frac{1}{q}) + 1}}{(\Gamma(\alpha))^r (p(\alpha - 1) + 1)^{\frac{r}{p}} \left(r \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{q} + 1 \right) \right)} \left(\int_A^{M1_H} \left| {}^H\mathbb{D}_{M-}^{\alpha, \beta} f \right|^q \right)^{\frac{r}{q}}. \quad (118)$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.17 and properties (P) and (ii), see section 1. $\square$

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